

A Microbiological and Radiological Study in Subjects with Acute Pyelonephritis in K.R. Hospital, Mysuru

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Abstract:

Background: Pyelonephritis is a suppurative infection of the kidney often caused by bacterial infection, presenting in acute or chronic forms. Its incidence is notably high among women, and the disease can lead to significant complications, particularly in patients with diabetes mellitus and other structural abnormalities of the urinary tract.

Objective: This study aims to correlate microbiological and radiological characteristics of acute pyelonephritis cases and to correlate in hospital Outcome.

Methods: Study comprised of 80 subjects, adhering to specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Participant's laboratory and radiological data was analyzed to assess the severity and outcomes of the disease.

Results: In this study, 55% were males and 45% were females, with the majority aged between 61-70 years (31.2%). Comorbidities were prevalent in 98.8%. At admission 62.5% had abnormal Total WBC Count, 91.2% had elevated serum creatinine levels, 62.5% had positive urine culture and 7.5% had positive blood culture. Radiological findings on CT KUB revealed unilateral pyelonephritis in 31.3%, bilateral pyelonephritis in 37.5%, abscess formation in 16.3%, and emphysematous pyelonephritis in 11.4%.

Conclusion: Leucocytosis, Worsening RFT, Pyuria and positive blood culture were well correlated with the disease. Emphysematous Pyelonephritis at presentation would portend the poor prognosis. Early Radiological imaging plays a crucial role in assessing the extent and severity of the disease, guiding appropriate intervention.

Keywords: Pyelonephritis, diabetes mellitus, CT KUB.

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Introduction

Pyelonephritis is suppurative infection of kidney affecting the renal parenchyma, calices, and pelvis, and can be acute, recurring, or chronic. The word comes from the Greek word "pyelo" (pelvis), "nephros" (kidney), and "-itis" (inflammation) [1,2].

APN was defined as the presence of two of the following: (a) axillary temperature $\geq 38.3^{\circ}\text{C}$ or chills; (b) flank pain or costovertebral angle tenderness or pain on bimanual palpation of the kidney; and (c) micturitional syndrome (including two or more of the following; dysuria, frequency, suprapubic pain, or urgency) together with the presence of pyuria (a positive leukocyte esterase dipstick test result, subsequently confirmed by urinalysis with more than ten leukocytes/mL in urine without centrifuging or more than five leukocytes per high-power field in centrifuged sediment) or a positive urine culture. [3] the most prevalent causes of complicated pyelonephritis are

diabetes mellitus, Structural and Functional abnormality of urinary tract, obstruction, stones, and pregnancy. Preterm labour and delivery may occur and lead to poor foetal outcomes, as with any febrile illness in later pregnancy [4].

The incidence of acute pyelonephritis remains significant, particularly among women. In the United States, it is estimated that there are approximately 459,000 to 1.1 million cases annually, with women being five times more likely than men to be hospitalized for the condition. Globally, the incidence ranges from 10.5 million to 25.9 million cases annually. Acute pyelonephritis is notably more prevalent in women aged 15-35, with a high incidence rate of 12-13 cases per 10,000 women per year (Oxford Academic). Recent studies also highlight that men, although less frequently affected, tend to have a higher mortality rate when hospitalized for severe cases of pyelonephritis. Factors such as older age, the

presence of comorbid conditions like diabetes, and complications such as septic shock or disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) significantly increase the risk of mortality

A familial susceptibility to pyelonephritis has been reported and attributed to polymorphisms with decreased expression of CXCR1, an IL-8 receptor [5]

The clinical range of acute pyelonephritis ranges from mild illness to Pyonephrosis and Emphysematous Pyelonephritis with a fulminant course. Emphysematous pyelonephritis (EPN) is a Urological Emergency caused by gas forming Uropathogens. Gas is localized in and around the kidneys in pyelonephritis [6]. Escherichia coli is the most frequent cause of pyelonephritis. Its possible virulence factors include the ability to adhere and colonize the urinary tract, an important initiating factor in all urinary tract infections. [7] Pyelonephritis severity cannot be determined solely by clinical or laboratory measures alone. Therefore, radiological imaging such as USG abdomen and pelvis and CTKUB, is necessary to determine the kind, extent, and severity of the disease as well as to decide intervention. Computed tomography (CT) scanning is the definitive imaging test for EPN [8,9].

The goal of the study is to correlate the radiological, microbiological, and clinical characteristics of cases of acute pyelonephritis in our community.

Objectives

1. To Study Microbiological and Radiological Profile in Acute Pyelonephritis
2. And to correlate in hospital Outcome.

Materials and Methods

Study design: Prospective Observational study.

Study period: 12 months: Aug 2022 to Aug 2023

Study population: 80 subjects

Primary Data: Patients with Acute pyelonephritis admitted in medical and surgical wards in KR Hospital, Mysuru.

Secondary Data: Published articles, journals, books and related websites

Statistical Methods: After Taking Institutional Ethical Clearance, Nature of the Study was explained to the Patient & Patient Party.

Written Informed Consent was taken.

Relevant History and Clinical Examination was done.

CBC, RFT, blood Culture, Urine Routine, Urine Culture & Sensitivity, USG Abdomen & Pelvis, CTKUB was done.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with Acute Pyelonephritis.
- Age > 18 Yrs

Exclusion Criteria:

- Single Kidney
- Renal Transplant Recipients
- Pregnancy
- Malignancies

Sample size Estimation

Sample Size: The sample size was decided in consultation with the statistician

Sample Size was calculated using the formula $n = Z^2 PQ / d^2$ where Z is the two tailed probability for 95% CI=1.96

P(Prevalence) = 29.7%

D(Precision) = 10%

$N = 3.84 * 29.7 * 70.3$

100

N = 80

Inferential statistics methods was chi-square test

Results

Study Was Done to Assess and Compare Various Microbiological And Radiological Profile In Apn Subjects And The Results Were As Follows.

1. Distribution Of Study Population Based On Age:

Table 1: Age Distribution of Study Population

Age	20-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-70	71-80
No of Subjects	2	12	15	19	25	7
% of Subjects	2.5%	15%	18.8%	23.8%	31.2%	8.8%

Figure 1: Age Distribution of Study Population

Study was done in 80 subjects and distributed based on age. In this study, maximum number of subjects (31.2%) were in the age group 61-70 years, 23.8% in 51-60 age group, 18.8% in 41-50

age group, 15% in 31-40 age group, 8.8% in 71-80 age group, 2.5% in 20-30 age group.

2. Distribution of Study Population Based on Gender:

Table 2: Distribution of study population based on gender

Sex	Male	Female
No Of Subjects	44	36
% Of Subjects	55%	45%

Figure 2: Distribution of study population based on gender

In this study, Out of 80 subjects, 55 percent of them were male and 45 percent of them were females

3. Distribution Of Study Population Based On Total WBC Count:

Table 3: Distribution of Study Population based on Total WBC count

Total WBC Count	Frequency	Percent
Normal	30	37.5
Abnormal	50	62.5
Total	80	100.0

Normal WBC count was considered between 4000-11000 cells/microlitre

Figure 3: Distribution of study population based on Total WBC count

37.5% of subjects had normal total count and 62.5% of subjects had abnormal total WBC count.

4. Distribution of Study Population Based on RFT

Table 4: Distribution of study population based on RFT

RFT	Frequency	Percent
Normal	7	8.8
Abnormal	73	91.2
Total	80	100.0

Figure 4: Distribution of study population based on RFT

Majority (91.2%) of subjects had abnormal RFT and 8.8% of subjects had normal RFT.

Table 5: Chi-square tests for Total WBC count and RFT

	Total Count	RFT
Chi-square	5.000	54.450
Df	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	0.025	0.000

However from above table since p value for RFT is 0.00, it showed significant association with the disease.

5. Distribution of Study Population Based on Urine Routine:

Table 5: Distribution of study population based on pus cells in urine routine

PUS CELLS/ HPF	Frequency	Percent
<10	8	10.0
11-100	39	48.8
100-200	10	12.5
Plenty	23	28.8
Total	80	100.0

Figure 5: Distribution of study population based on pus cells in urine routine

For the above distribution, chi-square value was 30.700, DF being 3, p value was found to be .000 48.8% of subjects had 11-100 pus cells/HPF, 28.8% had plenty pus cells/HPF, 12.5% had 100-200 pus cells/HPF, 10% had less than 10 pus

cells/HPF. Abnormal urine routine showed significant association with the disease.

6. Distribution Of Study Population Based On Urine Culture:

Table 6: Distribution of study population based on growth of organisms in urine culture

Organisms	Frequency	Percent
No growth	30	37.5
E coli	16	20.0
Mixed Growth	13	16.3
Enterococcus	12	15.0
Klebsiella	5	6.3
Non albicans candida	4	5.0
Total	80	100.0

Figure 6: Distribution of study population based on growth of organisms in urine culture

Majority(37.5%) of subjects had no growth (Sterile Pyuria) in urine culture.20% of subjects had E coli in culture, 16.3% had Mixed Growth, 15.0% had Enterococcus, rest had Klebsiella and Non albicans candida. For the above distribution, chi-square

value was 55.246, DF being 5, p value was found to be .000. Growth in urine culture showed significant association with the disease.

7. Distribution Of Study Population Based On Blood Culture:

Table 7: Distribution of study population based on growth of organisms in blood culture

Blood-Culture	Frequency	Percent
Normal	74	92.5
MRSA	2	2.5
E coli	4	5.0
Total	80	100.0

Figure 7: Distribution of study population based on growth of organisms in blood culture

Majority of subjects had no growth, 5% had E Coli and 2.5% had MRSA in urine culture. For the above distribution, chi-square value was 126.100, DF being 2, p value was found to be .000 Growth in blood culture showed significant association with the disease.

8. Distribution Of Study Population Based On Ultrasound KUB Parameters:

Table 8: Distribution of study population based on ultrasound KUB parameters

Usg Parameters	Bulky Kidneys	Increased Renal Echo Pattern	Hydronephrosis	Others
Frequency	58	35	6	10
Percent	72.5	43.8	7.5	12.5
Chi-square	1.500	1.250	57.800	45.000
Df	3	1	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	.682	.264	.000	.000

Figure 8: Distribution of study population based on ultrasound KUB parameters

72.5% of subjects had Bulky kidneys in USG, 43.8% had increased renal echo pattern, 7.5% had hydronephrosis and 12.5% had cysts, calculi and structural abnormalities like horseshoe kidneys. Presence of Hydronephrosis and cysts, calculi and

other structural abnormalities had significant association with the disease.

9. Distribution Of Study Population Based On CT-KUB:

Table 9: Distribution of study population based on CTKUB parameters

Ct-Kub Parameters	Bulky Kidney	Fat-Stranding	Abscess	Hydro-Nephrosis	Emphysematous Pyelonephritis	Cyst/Stone
Frequency	55	51	13	11	9	4
Percent	68.7	63.8	16.2	13.7	11.2	5
Chi-square	12.100	6.050	91.525	160.300	173.400	64.800
Df	3	1	2	3	3	1

Figure 9: Distribution of study population based on CTKUB parameters

Majority (68.7%) of subjects had bulky kidneys in CT-KUB, 63.8% had fat stranding, 16.2% had Renal abscess, 13.7% had Hydronephrosis, 11.2% had emphysematous changes, Rest had Cysts, calculi and other structural abnormalities. All the

factors in CT-KUB showed significant association with the disease.

10. Distribution of Study Population Based on Presence of Emphysematous Pyelonephritis on Ct kub

Table 10: Distribution of study population based on presence of emphysematous pyelonephritis on CTKUB

	Frequency	Percent
Emphysematous Change	9	11.3
No Emphysematous Change	71	88.8
Total	80	100.0

Figure 10: Distribution of study population based on presence of emphysematous pyelonephritis on CTKUB

9 out of 80 subjects had Emphysematous changes in CT-KUB. Presence of Emphysematous Changes in CTKUB showed significant association with the disease as the p value was found to be .000.

11. Comparison of Outcome with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis and Non-Emphysematous Pyelonephritis:

Table 11: Comparison of outcome with Emphysematous and Non Emphysematous Pyelonephritis:

		Outcome		Total
		Survived	Died	
Emphysematous Pyelonephritis	Number	0	9	9
	% within Outcome	0.0%	33.3%	11.2%
Non- Emphysematous Pyelonephritis	Number	53	18	71
	% within Outcome	100.0%	66.7%	88.8%
Total	Number	53	27	80
	% within Outcome	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.906	1	0.000

Presence of Emphysematous Pyelonephritis showed significant association with the Outcome with 100% Mortality in our study.

Conclusion

Majority of the study subjects were Elderly Diabetics. The Leucocytosis, Worsening RFT, Pyuria and positive blood culture were well correlated with the disease. Emphysematous Pyelonephritis at presentation would portend the poor prognosis. Most patients respond to appropriate antibiotic management within 48 to 72 hours, and those who do not should be evaluated with imaging and repeat cultures while alternative diagnoses are considered. [10]

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